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THE ROLE OF VISIONARY LEADERSHIP IN MAKING AN ORGANIZATION SUCCESSFUL IN THE PRESENT COMPETITIVE ERA

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Abstract

Today in the age of globalization where we are facing cut throat competition and a number of brands are available and where the customer is having wide variety of choice, which is available it is quite a difficult task to survive. And as we say only those survive who are competent and have the guts to be ahead of all others in terms of quality will survive and here the role of a visionary is very important here is the prominent role of the leader. Who have the vision paves the way leads them, motivates them and help them to achieve the target set. The present paper is focusing on the role of the leader; the data will be collected through secondary sources. It majorly focuses on the conceptual aspects leading to a personality who is being termed as a visionary.

Keywords: *organization, globalization, competition & strategy*

Introduction:

Leader is a person who makes the organization and is the person who is behind the breaking of the organization as well. He is the catalyst behind every organization, his role is of utmost importance and which paves the way through which the organization works. It is a process by which one person influences the thoughts, attitudes, and behaviors of others. Leaders set a direction for the rest of us; they help us see what lies ahead; they help us visualize what we might achieve; they encourage us and inspire us. Without leadership a group of human beings quickly degenerates into argument and conflict, because we see things in different ways and lean toward different solutions. Leadership helps to point us in the same direction and harness our efforts jointly.

Effective leaders recognize that the processes, steps, and methods of leadership are achieved with and through people. The dynamic changes in the business environment today dictate that leaders engage their team members to accomplish an inspirational vision. Effective leaders inspire and motivate those around them become enthusiastic followers who are committed to achieving the vision.

Leadership is about capacity: the capacity of leaders to listen and observe, to use their expertise as a starting point to encourage dialogue between all levels of decision-making, to establish processes and transparency in decision-making, to articulate their own value and visions clearly but not impose them. Leadership is about setting and not just reacting to agendas, identifying problems, and initiating change that makes for substantial improvement rather than managing change. Leadership is about innovators and change agents; seeing the big picture, thinking strategically about how to attain goals, and working (with the help of others) to achieve the goals.

A leader focusing on the human dimension is concerned about building a sense of citizenship among a much larger group of people. It is built around a process that invites much broader participation and relies on input from many others outside of the top team. The aim is to create a sense of belonging and ownership across the organization. In this situation many more people feel they can have an informed opinion about the overall strategy. They believe they have been part of its development, and that they can influence the outcome. In that sense, it is their strategy.

Leadership presents challenges that call forth the best in people, and bring them together around a shared sense of purpose. With intentionality, alignment, and a higher purpose; the work between the leader and the followers create a synergy. Despite what style of leadership, the various styles can support one another to achieve the goals of the organization. Strategic leadership can only be achieved when the leader is strategic in their approach to the matters of the organization.

The present era is the of innovation, change and only those survive who are ready to accept the changes that are taking place around the globe, traditionally, it has been seen the role of a leader is to make sure that the task allotted to him should be well addressed even by the people who are part of the team but the onus remains on the leader only. On the other hand leadership must be seen as a relationship between the leader & followers.

Visionary leaders are uncommon, but they share many characteristics. The qualities of visionary leaders include openness, imagination, persistence, and conviction. This article discusses these various qualities of visionary leaders. Albert Einstein and Thomas Edison are examples of great visionaries. Visionaries possess an unusually large degree of openness to new information. This openness may or may not extent to people. Inflexible people, once they make up their mind, cannot be persuaded, nor do they continue to search for or take in new information.

Features of visionary leadership:

Underlying characteristics or features of a visionary leader are as follows:

- **Excellent communicator**
- **Charismatic leader**
- **Organizer as well as risk taker**
- **Strategic planner & have a strong conviction.**
- **Charismatic leader are open and persistent.**

EXCELLENT COMMUNICATOR:

A visionary leader has good communication skills. HE or She knows how to verbalize the dreams and goals and can explain them to his team. For the leader, communication isn't just one-sided. In addition to sharing her vision for the future, a visionary leader is also an active listener. As more people "catch the vision," leaders listen to their ideas and thoughts, incorporating them into the larger goal. Visionaries involve others in reaching their milestones and help the team members meet their personal goals. Excellent communication bridges even the slightest gap a leader is having with the follower

CHARISMATIC LEADER:

Visionary leaders also have charisma. Merriam-Webster defines charisma as a "personal magic of leadership arousing special popular loyalty." Not everyone is born with this "personal magic," but they can learn and cultivate it. Charisma is a natural attraction that draws people to the leader and the leader's enthusiasm. This is natural.

Out of the various styles of leader charismatic leaders are regarded as one of the most popular styles as they are the people who are popular due to the personal magic, the biggest example are Mahatma Gandhi, Nelson Mandela etc. these leaders become popular due to the personal quality of being different in their approach, being firm as well as determined in their conduct.

Organizer as well as risk taker

Visionary leaders also are chief organizers. While many leaders have administrators that manage the processes, the leader often sets up the organization by establishing key departments or functions. As the organizer-in-chief, the

visionary directs, develops and conducts meetings until reliable help is found. During the initial organization, a leader will take the time build a solid foundation through establishing boards, councils or a company hierarchy.

Visionary leaders, like Washington, are notable risk-takers. These leaders are willing to gamble on something they believe in, but the gamble is often a measured one. Visionaries are creative people that take the initiative with the appropriate action. Visionaries take intelligent risks that capitalize on prime conditions. This kind of leader starts small by taking measured steps than later bigger risks

Strategic planner & have a strong conviction:

Visionary leaders are strategic planners. Like a chess player, these leaders plan ahead to make the best business moves. Strategic planning involves creating an action plan with a particular strategy in mind. The leader's vision defines what the organization will look like in the future and how it will function. His strategies are designed to take him toward his ultimate vision

Conviction is actually strong belief or opinion about something.

Several specific traits support the development of the quality of conviction in a visionary leader. One such trait is the willingness to take calculated risks. In order to form conviction, a visionary leader must be willing to lay it all on the line for a worthy cause. Similarly, a certain amount of discontent with the status quo is necessary for one to be willing to lay things on the line. In addition, an unconventional nature is somewhat helpful in that it tends to make one immune to negative social pressures that are experienced as naysayers constantly doubt the vision and the visionary.

Visionary leader are open and persistent:

Innovation and advancement had made a persistent change in the working of an organization. A leader is regarded to be the change agent who has to bring that change in the environment of the organization as he makes the changes possible for the organization.

One specific challenge unique to visionary leaders is best expressed by the warning label on a driver's mirror, "objects in mirror are [further] than they appear." Because of the vividness of their visions, visionaries often underestimate the difficulty in bringing the vision into reality or the "distance" between the present and envisioned outcome (as the vision seems so close and obtainable to them).

The other challenge faced by visionary leaders is that they tend to have dreams that are larger and more difficult than average persons, and thus an extraordinary degree of persistence is required.

Visionary Leadership & its Importance In today's Scenario:

Organization are getting diversified and they are also changing a lot due to the technological upgradation as well due to the changes taking place in the business world. The very essence of leadership is that you have to have a vision. Good leaders are made not born. If you have the desire and will power, you can become an effective leader. Good leaders develop through a never ending process of self –study, education, training, and experience.

To inspire your people into higher levels of teamwork, there are certain things you must be, know and do. These do not come naturally, but are acquired through continual work and study. The best leaders are continually working and studying to improve their leadership skills.

Before we get started, let's define leadership. Leadership is a complex process by which a person influences others to accomplish a mission, task, or objective and directs the organization in a way that makes it more cohesive and

coherent. A person carries out this process by applying her leadership attributes (belief, values, ethics, character, knowledge, and skills). Although your position as a manager, supervisor, lead, etc. gives you the authority to accomplish certain tasks and objectives in the organization, this power does not make you a leader...it simply makes you the boss. Leadership makes people want to achieve high goals and objectives, while, on the other hand, bosses tell people to accomplish a task or objective. As a leadership, you need to interact with followers, peers, seniors, and other people whose support you need to accomplish your objectives. To gain their support, you must be able to understand and motivate them. To understand and motivate people, you must know human nature. Human nature is the common qualities of all people have similar needs. As a leader you must understand these needs because they are powerful motivators.

Conclusion:

Leadership is considered to be the heart of management of any organization, an organization will only flourish if the leader is having a strong conviction and most importantly vision to do well in whatever he is doing. It will be of paramount importance for an organization to make sure that the leaders are given full autonomy with respect to their position in the organization to make it a success which would be reflecting in the working as well. As when he is being given a free hand in the decision making as well as working of the organization, he will be able to have a strong conviction to achieve what he is expecting to have in the organization, the people will also listen to him as he will be able to live up to their expectation which will enable them to believe in their free will.

Vision is something which will be able to make an impact on the achievement of goals of an organization, leader plays the role of a catalyst in an organization, therefore is quite important. The people who are only following him if he is able to reciprocate in the right manner leading to better results which will be ultimately seen in the results of an organization. Therefore the role of visionary leader will definitely help an organization achieve what they are expecting to achieve.

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